

Metadata Template

Title of dataset	<i>Carbon dioxide and methane dynamics in a peatland headwater stream: origins, processes and implication</i>
Keywords	<i>Headwater streams, Peatlands, Methane, Carbon dioxide, Biogeochemical aquatic fluxes, Stable isotopes</i>
Lead author for the dataset	<i>Pierre Taillardat</i>
Title and position of lead author	<i>Research Fellow</i>
Organization and address of lead author	<i>Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada Current addresses: National University of Singapore</i>
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Additional authors or contributors to the dataset	<i>Pascal Bodmer, Alex Ponçot, Antonin Prijac, Khawla Riahi, Charles P. Deblois, Laure Gandois, Paul A. del Giorgio, Marc André Bourgault, Alain Tremblay, and Michelle Garneau</i>
Organization associated with the data	<i>Same as for lead author</i>
Funding	<i>This research was funded by the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada and Hydro-Quebec to Michelle Garneau (RDCPJ 514218-17).</i>
License	<i>CCBY</i>
Geographic location – verbal description	<i>The data was collected in a boreal peatland in Côte Nord, Québec, Canada (50°31'N; 63°12'W, elevation: 108 ± 5 m asl).</i>
Time frame - Begin date	<i>01/06/2019 (MM/DD/YYYY)</i>
Time frame - End date	<i>10/10/2020 (MM/DD/YYYY)</i>
General study design	<i>This study was led by Michelle Garneau's lab in collaboration with researchers from other institutions in Quebec and France. In total, the study site was visited monthly and automated continuous equipment were left on the site between visits.</i>
Methods description	<i>Please refer to the manuscript for full description of the methods used.</i>
Quality control	<i>All data were carefully checked by at least two coauthors.</i>

Figure2_Alongthestream.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Period	Sampling period ()	YYB#fieldvisit (e.g., 19B1 for 1 st visit of 2019)	Blank
Stream_rank	Sampling site position along the stream from upstream to downstream	Numerical value	Blank

Distance_m	Sampling site distance from the most upstream point	meter	Blank
Year	Sampling year	Numerical value	Blank
Sampling_date	Sampling date	dd-mm-yy	Blank
AtmP_Pa	Atmospheric pressure	Pascal	Blank
pCH4_ppm	Stream dissolved CH ₄ partial pressure (median value from triplicates)	Part per million (ppm)	Blank
stdev_pCH4_ppm	Stream dissolved CH ₄ partial pressure (standard deviation value from triplicates)	Part per million (ppm)	Blank
pCO2_ppm	Stream dissolved CO ₂ partial pressure (median value from triplicates)	Part per million (ppm)	Blank
stdev_pCO2_ppm	Stream dissolved CO ₂ partial pressure (standard deviation value from triplicates)	Part per million (ppm)	Blank
d13CCH4_permil	Stream dissolved $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ value (median value from triplicates)	permil	Blank
stdev_d13CCH4_permil	Stream dissolved $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ value (standard deviation value from triplicates)	permil	Blank
d13CCO2_permil	Stream dissolved $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ value (median value from triplicates)	permil	Blank
stdev_d13CCO2_permil	Stream dissolved $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ value (standard deviation value from triplicates)	permil	Blank
WTemp_degC	Water temperature	Degrees celsius	Blank

Figure3_massbalancemodels.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Location_ID	Sampling site location (and associated local watershed area)	-	Blank
Campaign	Sampling campaign	MMM-yy	Blank
Sampling_Date	Sampling date	dd-mm-yy	Blank
Sampling_Time	Sampling time	HH:MM	Blank

Latitude	Sampling site latitudinal coordinated		Blank
Longitude	Sampling site longitudinal coordinated		Blank
Catchment_area_m2	Sampling site catchment area	Square meter	Blank
Stream_surface_area_m2	Stream surface area for this specific section	Square meter	Blank
SectionLength_m			
width_m	Stream width	Meter	Blank
V_ms1	Flow velocity	Meter per second	Blank
depth_m	Stream depth	Meter	Blank
Q_m3_s	Water discharge	Cubic meter per second	Blank
DOC_mgL1	Dissolved Organic Carbon	Milligram carbon per liter	Blank
pCO2_ppm	Partial pressure of dissolved CO2	Part per million	Blank
pCH4_ppm	Partial pressure of dissolved CH4	Part per million	Blank
atm_CO2_ppm	Atmospheric concentrations of CO2	Part per million	Blank
atm_CH4_ppm	Atmospheric concentrations of CH4	Part per million	Blank
air_pressure_kPa	Atmospheric pressure	kilopascal	Blank
water_temp_C	Water temperature	Degrees Celsius	Blank
water_temp_K	Water temperature	Kelvin	Blank
measuredmedian_CO2_flux_mmol_m2_h	CO ₂ flux at the interface water-atmosphere using a floating chamber (median value from n values)	Micromole per square meter per hour	Blank
measuredmean_CO2_flux_mmol_m2_h	CO ₂ flux at the interface water-atmosphere using a floating chamber (mean value from n values)	Micromole per square meter per hour	Blank
stdev_measured_CO2_flux	CO ₂ flux at the interface water-atmosphere using a floating chamber	Micromole per square meter per hour	Blank

	(standard deviation value from n values)		
n_measured_CO2_flux	Number of CO ₂ flux measurement replicates	Numerical value	Blank
measuredmedian_CH4_flux_mmol_m2_h	CH ₄ flux at the interface water-atmosphere using a floating chamber (median value from n values)	Micromole per square meter per hour	Blank
measuredmean_CH4_flux_mmol_m2_h	CH ₄ flux at the interface water-atmosphere using a floating chamber (mean value from n values)	Micromole per square meter per hour	Blank
stdev_measured_CH4_flux	CH ₄ flux at the interface water-atmosphere using a floating chamber (standard deviation value from n values)	Micromole per square meter per hour	Blank
n_measured_CH4_flux	Number of CO ₂ flux measurement replicates	Numerical value	Blank
Sol_CO2	Coefficient solubility of carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	NA	Blank
Sol_CH4	Coefficient solubility of methane	NA	Blank
water_pCO2_uatm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ in water	Micro atmosphere	Blank
water_pCH4_uatm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ in water	Micro atmosphere	Blank
Q_Ls1	Water discharge	Liter per second	Blank
CO2_load_umols1	Carbon dioxide downstream export	Micromole per second	Blank
CH4_load_umols1	Methane downstream export	Micromole per second	Blank
DOC_load_umols1	Dissolved organic carbon downstream export	Micromole per second	Blank

Figure4a_rain.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-
Rain_mm_Tot	Cumulative rain	mm	NA

Figure4b_Figure8_discharge.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-
Q_m3_s	Water discharge at the outlet	Cubic meter per second	-
Q_l_s	Water discharge at the outlet	Liter per second	-

Figure4c_Figure8_CO2CH4timeseries.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-
CO2_ppm	Partial pressure of CO ₂ at the outlet station (#8)	Part per million	Blank
CH4_ppm	Partial pressure of CH ₄ at the outlet station (#8)	Part per million	Blank
Temp_degC	Water temperature	Degrees Celsius	Blank
pH	pH	unitless	Blank
SPC_us_cm	Specific conductivity	Micro Siemens per centimeter	Blank
DO_sat	Dissolved oxygen	Percentage of saturation in water	Blank
DO_mgL	Dissolved oxygen	Milligram per liter	Blank
AtmP_kPa	Atmospheric pressure	Kilo Pascal	Blank

Figure4d_WTD.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
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Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-
WTD_m	Water table depth	meter	NA
WTD_m_pred	Gap filled water table depth	meter	NA

Figure5a_24hpatterns.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-
pCO2_Norm	Normalized partial pressure of carbon dioxide	NA	NA
pCO2_Norm	Normalized partial pressure of methane	NA	NA
pO2_Norm	Normalized partial pressure of oxygen		

Figure5b_24hStableIsotopes.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-
d13C-CO2	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ stable isotope value of carbon dioxide	‰	NA
d13C-CH4	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ stable isotope value of methane	‰	NA

Figure6_CO2CH4WTD.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy	-
Rain_mm_Tot	Cumulative rain	mm	NA
Rain_event	Rain event	1=yes; 0=no	NA
CO2_dailymax_uM	Daily maximum dissolved CO2 concentration	Micromole per cubic meter	NA
CH4_dailymax_uM	Daily maximum dissolved CH4 concentration	Micromole per cubic meter	NA

WTDmax_m	Maximum daily water table depth	Meter	NA
WTDmax_2_m	Average of the daily maximum water table depth for the last two previous days	Meter	NA
WTDmax_3_m	Average of the daily maximum water table depth for the last three previous days	Meter	NA
WTDmax_n_m	Average of the daily maximum water table depth for the last n previous days	Meter	NA

Figure7_C-GHGlosses.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date	Measurement date	dd-mm-yy	-
CO2_evasion_mold	Carbon dioxide emission to the atmosphere	Mol per day	NA
CH4_evasion_mold	Methane emission to the atmosphere	Mol per day	NA
CO2_load_mold	Carbon dioxide downstream export	Mol per day	NA
CH4_load_mold	Methane downstream export	Mol per day	NA
C.GHG_Tot_mold	Sum of the carbon dioxide and methane emission to the atmosphere and downstream export	Mol per day	NA
CO2_contrib_%	Contribution of carbon dioxide in the total carbon greenhouse gas loss	percentage	NA
CH4_contrib_%	Contribution of methane in the total carbon greenhouse gas loss	percentage	NA
Evasion_contrib_%	Contribution of atmospheric emissions in the total carbon greenhouse gas loss	percentage	NA
Export_contrib_%	Contribution of downstream export in the	percentage	NA

	total carbon greenhouse gas loss		
WTD_m	Water table depth daily average	meter	NA
Q_m3d1	Water discharge daily rates	Cubic meter per day	NA

Figure7b_CH4losses.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-
Value	CH4 loss	Mol per hour	NA
Condition	Type of loss	A: downstream export (CH4_load_molh1) B: atmospheric emission (CH4_evasion_molh)	NA

Figure7b_CH4losses.csv

	Description	Unit or code explanation or date format	Empty value code
Date_Time	Measurement date and time	dd-mm-yy HH:MM	-
Value	CH4 loss	Mol per hour	NA
Condition	Type of loss	A: downstream export (CH4_load_molh1) B: atmospheric emission (CH4_evasion_molh)	NA